

Method development, validation and color development studies for amoxicillin trihydrate in its pharmaceutical dosage using ponceau 4R reagent by spectrophotometry, HPLC and proton NMR spectroscopy

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Abstract : The method developed is based on pK_a values and proton exchange concept, in which ponceau 4R reagent ($pK_a = -2.8$) reacts with amoxicillin ($pK_a = 3.39$), both of which are colorless solutions in protonated form. On mixing these compounds at suitable conditions, pale red color develops at room temperature. It is predicted that ponceau 4R undergoes proton exchange and forms salt based on number of carboxylate anions in amoxicillin. The formation of ionic solution, by mixing of amoxicillin and ponceau 4R imparts color to the resultant solution. The resultant ionic solution shows maximum absorbance at wavelength, $\lambda_{max} = 509$ nm. The method complies with Beer's law at concentration range, 10–50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The coefficient correlation was 0.999 for the linear curve equation, $Y = 0.030x + 0.021$. Method detection limit (MDL), limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), lower critical limit (LCL), upper critical limit (UCL), signal noise ratio (SNR), t -value, p -value and confidence interval were calculated for the ionic solution of amoxicillin and ponceau 4R. Average recovery of amoxicillin solution was made to 100.6. The method validated is as per International conference on harmonization (ICH) and association of analytical communities (AOAC) guidelines. The method was found to be simple, accurate, and economical. Amoxicillin and its colored ionic solution were testified on RP-HPLC. ^1H NMR spectrum of the drug and the ionic solution formed was also recorded to verify the possible mechanism. The ionic solution was stable up to 12 h.

Keywords : Ponceau 4R, amoxicillin, visible spectrophotometry, HPLC, ^1H NMR.

Introduction

Amoxicillin¹ (Fig. 1) is a moderate spectrum β -lactum class of drug. Chemically it is [(2*S*,5*R*,6*R*)-6((2*R*)-2-amino)-3,3-dimethyl-7-oxo-4-thia-1-azabicyclo(3.2.0)]-heptanes-2-carboxylic acid, which is a known antibiotic agent. The validation of Amoxicillin by spectrophotometry^{2,3}, LC⁴, HPLC⁵, voltammetry⁶, flow injection⁷ and by thin layer chromatography⁸ were reported earlier. Sodium salt of ponceau 4R (Fig. 2) is chemically tri sodium (8*Z*)-7-oxo-8-[(4-sulfonatophthalen-1-yl)hydrazinylidene]naphthalene-1,3-disulfonate, widely used as food colorant (color index 16225). Reagent based color development method is simple and use of such reagents for validation⁹ was found to be reliable. Further, no method development and validation of amoxicillin was reported using ponceau 4R, supported by HPLC and ^1H NMR spectroscopy. ICH¹⁰⁻¹² and AOAC¹³ guidelines were followed in the present study. Amoxicillin is sodium salt of

Fig. 1. Amoxicillin.

Fig. 2. Ponceau 4R reagent.

Table-2 (contd.)

carboxylic acid, which undergoes proton exchange/acid-base reaction to regenerate the pale red color of ponceau 4R reagent. UV-Visible spectroscopy is a simple, accurate and sensitive analytical method, which finds its way in advancement of green analytical approaches^{14,15}.

Results and discussion

The method development involves proton exchange reaction between ponceau 4R and amoxicillin leading to formation of pale red to pink color. The color developed is directly proportional to the drug concentration, which was validated in accordance with the ICH. The color developed was stable upto 12 h, which suggest that the sample is stable till the validation is completed. The optical and statistical parameters (Tables 1 and 2) were calculated and were found to be within the limits. The method developed was further supported by pK_a values¹⁶. Method detection limit (MDL), limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), lower critical limit (LCL), upper critical limit (UCL), signal to noise ratio (SNR), *t*-value, *p*-value, confidence interval and Sandells sensitivity^{17,18} were calculated. Further, HPLC and NMR spectrum was recorded to support the method.

Repeatability	Valid for intra-/inter-day
Ruggedness	Valid
Robustness	Valid
Solution stability	12 h
Limit of quantization	0.73
Limit of detection	2.20
Lower critical limit (LCL)	0.0096
Upper critical limit (UCL)	0.033
Method detection limit (MDL)	0.0151

The pK_a value¹⁹ of amoxicillin is 3.39 and of ponceau 4R reagent is -2.8, suggests that ponceau is a stronger acid than amoxicillin. Further, when the reagent is protonated, it becomes colorless (286 nm) and when it donates H⁺ ion to the amoxicillin it forms salt of sulphonic acid, which is colored (Scheme 1). The salt of ponceau 4R shows maximum absorbance at wavelength of 509 nm. The colored sodium salt of ponceau 4R reagent (R-SO₃⁻Na⁺) on protonation at pH = 6.5 forms sulphonic acid

Table 1. Analytical/statistical validation parameters

Validation parameter	Analytical/statistical data
Absorption wave length (λ _{max})	509 nm
Average of absorbance	0.924
Length of the cell	1 cm
Concentration of amoxicillin	0.310
Concentration of ponceau	0.8096 mol/dm ³
Concentration range	10-50 ppm
Average of concentration	0.924
Molar absorptivity	38290.5 M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
Optical density	0.031
Transmittance	48.90%
Sandell sensitivity	0.77
Signal-noise ratio	1.965
<i>t</i> -Value	0.505
<i>p</i> -Value	0.628

Scheme 1

(R-SO₃H), which is colorless solution. Amoxicillin present in the dosage form is also colorless in its solution form. In the salt form amoxicillin contains sodium and carboxylate ions (R-COO⁻Na⁺). On mixing ponceau 4R solution with amoxicillin solution, pale red color devel-

Table 2. Analytical data as per ICH

Validation parameter	Analytical data
Linear equation	Y = 0.030x + 0.021
Slope	0.030
Regression co-efficient	0.999
Average recovery	100.67

ops, due to transfer of protons from reagent to the drug molecule. In this process ponceau 4R regains its original sodium salt form, which is colored. The transfer of protons can be explained on the basis of acidic strength, as sulphonic acid is stronger Bronsted acid, which donates protons readily to amoxicillin having carboxylate anions which are basic in nature and act as Bronsted base (proton acceptor). The resultant solution is pale red ionic solution of reagent and the drug. The color developed is directly proportional to the concentration of ponceau 4R in the resultant ionic solution, which in turn depend upon the number of amoxicillin molecules. Thus, by measuring the intensity of the colored solution as per ICH guidelines, the concentration of amoxicillin can be accurately determined in its pharmaceutical dosage (Tables 1–8).

RP-HPLC (chromosil C₁₈ RP column of 250 × 4.6 mm), technique was used to check any possible chemical interaction between the reactants, i.e. formation of covalent bond. But the chromatogram of standard amoxicillin, novomoxin and the sample solution shows no change in the chromatogram obtained, which rules out the possibility of chemical reactivity leading to the formation of new adduct. The UV-Visible spectrophotometry also indicate that there is no chemical change in the structure of reactants, as the λ_{\max} (509 nm) of ponceau 4R in salt form and in the ionic solution remains unchanged.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of amoxicillin and its chemical shift values, support that there is no chemical reaction between amoxicillin and ponceau 4R reagent, as the chemical shift value of amoxicillin (δ 1.1 to 7.3) remain unchanged in the mixture. Similarly the NMR spectrum of ponceau reagent (δ 7.9 to 8.9) also remains unchanged in the ionic solution.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

The instruments used are, UV-Visible spectrophotometer, 1240 (Schimadzu), HPLC Instrument (Schimadzu prominence), ¹H NMR spectrophotometer 400 MHz (Bruker Biospin), analytical balance (Mettler Toledo B2048).

Reagents :

Pure amoxicillin trihydrate (API), amoxicillin capsules (Novamoxin, CIPLA) and salt of ponceau 4R (Chawla

essence mart) were used. Other chemical used were of analytical reagent grade.

Preparation of diluent solution :

0.68 g of KH₂PO₄ was accurately weighed and was taken in 100 ml distilled water and sonified. The solution pH was adjusted to 5.6 using 0.1 N HCl and 0.1 N NaOH solution. The resultant solution is referred to as diluent solution.

Preparation of dosage solution :

20 capsules of novomoxin were taken and from its powder, 10 mg of it was accurately weighed and transferred into 20 ml flask and was made up with diluent solution and sonified. It is labeled as 500 μ g/mL of dosage solution. Further its pH was adjusted to 7, using 0.1 N HCl and 0.1 N NaOH solution. The solution is labeled as dosage solution.

Preparation of standard solution :

10 mg of pure amoxicillin was dissolved in diluent solution and was sonified. Later its pH was adjusted to 7. The solution was then transferred into 20 ml standard flask and was made up with the diluent solution and labeled as 500 μ g/mL standard solution of amoxicillin.

Preparation of reagent solution :

Sodium salt of ponceau 4R is red color crystalline powder. 3.3 g of it was transferred into 20 ml standard flask and about 10 ml distilled water was added to it, whereby pale red color developed. By using 0.1 N HCl and 0.1 N NaOH, its pH was adjusted to 6.5, which turns colorless. This is due to protonation of R-SO₃⁻Na⁺ to form R-SO₃H. Finally the solution was made upto 20 ml with distilled water. The concentration of the resultant reagent solution is 0.136 M.

Method development :

10 ml of dosage solution and 10 ml of protonated ponceau 4R reagent solution were transferred into 100 ml standard flask and thoroughly shaken and allowed to stand for about 15 min. Pale red color of ponceau 4R reagent regenerates, which is further known as sample solution or the ionic solution. The concentration of the color developed in the ionic solution is directly proportional to the concentration of amoxicillin present in the pharmaceutical dosage form. The solution obeys Beer's law in

the concentration range 10–50 µg/mL. Other analytical parameters were also performed as per ICH guidelines²² to validate the proposed method.

Method validation :

Linearity and range :

The sample solution of amoxicillin of five different concentrations 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 ppm were subjected to absorbance at λ_{\max} 509 nm (Table 3). The drug obeyed Beer's law (Fig. 3) and the slope intercept was found to be $Y = 0.030x + 0.021$ and regression coefficient, $R^2 = 0.998$ were established from the values of absorbance.

Table 3. Linearity of sample solution

Concentration of sample solution (M)	Absorbance at λ_{\max} 509 nm
10	0.310
20	0.631
30	0.930
40	1.240
50	1.510

Fig. 3. Linearity plot.

Specificity :

In the present method, amoxicillin was selectively made to react with the reagent, ponceau 4R in the presence of placebo and impurities, according to standard ICH guideline. Hence the present method can be considered as specific.

Accuracy :

Recovery studies in the present work confirm that the method is accurate. 1 ml of the standard solution was taken and concentrations of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60 ppm were made (Table 4).

Table 4. Accuracy

% of Concentration level	% Recovery	Average recovery
80	99.712	100.67
100	99.913	
120	102.40	

Repeatability :

From the freshly prepared sample solutions of concentrations, 10, 20 and 30 ppm, intra-day precision and inter-day precision absorbance measurements were made (Table 5).

Table 5. Repeatability

Solution	Concentration (M)	Intra-day precision (%)	Inter-day precision (%)
Novomoxin	10	0.291	0.301
	15	0.432	0.461
	20	0.629	0.608
Ionic solution	10	0.319	0.299
	20	0.685	0.653
	30	0.811	0.910

Ruggedness :

For a freshly prepared sample solution of 35 ppm absorbance values were recorded on different days and were also recorded by two different analysts (Table 6).

Table 6. Ruggedness

Concentration derivative (ppm)	Factor considered	Absorbance
50	Day-1	1.482
	Day-2	1.498
50	Analyst-1	1.494
	Analyst-2	1.500

Robustness :

It involves scanning of the sample solution at different wavelength, temperature and values (Table 7). Absorbance recordings were made for the sample solution to testify the solutions robustness by varying factors.

Sample solution stability :

Sample solution of novomoxin in ponceau was freshly prepared and absorbance measurements were made at 0, 12, 24 and 48 h interval. In similar mode absorbance measurements were made for standard solution in same time frame as recorded for sample solution (Table 8).

Table 7. Robustness

Concentration derivative (<i>M</i>)	Factor considered	Absorbance
30	$\lambda_{\max} = 507$	1.501
	$\lambda_{\max} = 511$	1.508
30	pH = 6.0	1.481
	pH = 8.0	1.499
30	At 25 °C	1.500
	At 35 °C	1.482

Table 8. Solution stability

Compound	Time (h)	Absorbance
Novomoxicin	0	1.21
	12	1.10
	24	0.89
	48	-0.001
Ionic solution	0	1.18
	12	0.92
	24	0.30
	48	0.008

Fig. 4. Stability of amoxicillin

The stability change of amoxicillin with change in time is given in Fig. 4.

Conclusion

The method is simple, accurate and economical and can be used for validation of amoxicillin, utilizing the concept of pK_a and/or proton exchange technique, resulting in salt formation, which imparts color to the solution which is directly proportional to the concentration of the amoxicillin in the pharmaceutical dosage.

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